

INFECTION RATES OF CAMPYLOBACTER SPECIES IN HUMANS AND SLAUGHTERED BROILER-CHICKENS AT KERBALA RETAIL POINTS

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Abstract:

A cross-sectional study was done during the period from December 2021 to July 2022 to determine the prevalence of *Campylobacter* species and their infection rates in humans and slaughtered broiler-chickens at Kerbala province. A total of 260 samples were collected as follows: 40 cecal swabs were collected from different local markets distributed in Kerbala, 80 samples swabs from de-feathering machines and carcass rinse water, and 40 samples from local and imported frozen chickens, in addition to, 100 samples from people with diarrhea from Al-Hussain Medical City and General Children's Hospital at Kerbala (Iraq). All samples were subjected to the initial bacterial isolation processes on the special and distinctive culture media for *Campylobacter Spp.* Results showed that contamination rates of *Campylobacter* species were **26%** in broiler intestines, **12.5%** in carcass rinse water, **10%** from de-feathering machines and **7.5%** of frozen chickens. The rate of infection in humans was **6%** and results show that there is a significant (**p-value ≤ 0.05**) correlation between age and infection with *campylobacter spp.*, as the results show high infections in children under five years of age, and the incidence rate decreases with increasing age. Regarding the infection rates of *Campylobacter spp.* in slaughtered chickens, results showed that 16.25 % of samples collected from broiler intestines were found infected with *campylobacter spp.* and they represented the highest infection rate among other sources in slaughter process.

Key words: *Campylobacter*, infection rate, slaughtered broiler, Kerbala, retail points.

Introduction:

Every year, over 400 to 500 million infections with pathogenic *Campylobacter spp.* occur around the world . Infection with enteric *campylobacters* generally causes diarrhoea (Van Vliet and Ketley, 2001, Myintzaw *et al.*, 2022).

After infection with *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in immunologically naive patients, severe stomach discomfort, typically accompanied by fever and general malaise, occurs after 1 to 7 days. The symptoms progress to a lot of diarrhoea with mucus and blood in it. Infection with *Campylobacter jejuni* has been identified as a common cause of GBS (Nachamkin *et al.*, 1999).

When compared to other bacteria (for example, *Salmonella spp.*), *Campylobacter spp.* has a greater colonization capacity and intestinal carriage levels at slaughter of animals (Mead, 2004). *Campylobacters* are found in the natural gut flora of a variety of animals, both domestic and wild. Human infection is mainly acquired by the ingestion of undercooked infected meat or other

cross-contaminated food products. Fecal contamination of meat occurs often during slaughtering. *Campylobacter* spp., on the other hand, can be caught via untreated milk or contaminated water, as well as from pets with diarrhea (Kreling et al., 2020). Changes in eating patterns, rather than more knowledge or better diagnostic methods, are assumed to be behind the continued growth in *Campylobacter* infection (Van Vliet and Ketley, 2001).

It's also resistant to scorching, washing, and chilling, all of which help keep the number of other germs under control (Humphrey et al., 2007). This survival might be explained by the ability to link to chicken tissues during carcass processing (Mead, 2004). The presence of *Campylobacter* spp. in frozen poultry meat samples show that, while freezing might halt the fast development that occurs during the slaughter process, it is not enough to render this disease inert (Goh et al., 2014). There is evidence that the global incidence of *Campylobacter* has risen in the last ten years. Despite the lack of epidemiological data from Asia, the Middle East, or Africa, our findings support the idea that *Campylobacter* infections are prevalent in these areas. (Sadkowska-Todys and Kucharczyk, 2012). According to estimates, *Campylobacter* infection causes 7.5 million disability adjusted life years (DALYs) in diverse communities across the world, second only to rotavirus as a cause of diarrhea (Murray et al., 2012). To summarize, according to the 2015 global burden of illness estimate, over 25,000 children under the age of five years every year, with Africa and Asia having the highest rates (Murray et al., 2012).

Campylobacter species have become more common in recent years. Food-borne diseases are also becoming more common in high-income nations. The greatest incidences of campylobacteriosis are reported in Europe. (Facciola et al., 2017).

The aim of this study was to find out the infection rates of *Campylobacter* spp. in humans and slaughtered broiler-chickens at Kerbala retail points.

Materials and Methods:

Study design and Sample collection

A Cross-sectional study was performed to collect a total of 260 samples, from broiler chickens and humans. These samples were gathered from different locations in Karbala province and cultured in appropriate media according to internationally known protocols for bacterial cultivation and identification (MacFaddin 2000). Then it followed by the initial bacterial isolation process on the special and distinctive culture media of *Campylobacter* such as campylobacter agar and the followed propagation

Campylobacter Isolation and identification

Collected sample inoculated immediately onto C&S modified Carry Blair transport media then cultured on selective agar (campylobacter agar enriched with 5-10% blood), adding supplements and incubate in anaerobic jar for 48 hrs. at 42°C under microaerophilic condition. Suspected

colony was identified confirmed by Gram staining and examined under microscope, Biochemical testing (oxidase, catalase, Indoxyl hydrolysis), finally by Molecular Methods PCR.

Results:

1. Prevalence of *Campylobacter spp.* according to Sample Sources

1.1. Prevalence of *Campylobacter spp.* in Broilers Chicken

Campylobacter spp. were detected in 38 (23.75%) of 160 samples. Out of the 40 broiler intestine samples, the detection rate was 26 (16.25%), out of 40 isolates from de-feathering machines were 4 (2.5%) positive, out of 40 isolates from carcass rinse water were 5 (3.125%) positive and lower rates in frozen carcass from 40 isolates were 3 (1.785%) positive (Figure 1)

From the current results showed in Table (1), it turns out that there is a correlation between the bacteria and the site of infection, where the evidence showed a significant increase in the intestine when compared to De-feathering machines and carcass rinse water (p-value ≤ 0.01).

The results of the current study illustrated in Table 1 showed that there is non-significant (p>0.05) relationship between the location of samples taken and *Campylobacter* infection rate.

Figure (1): Infection rates of *campylobacter spp.* in slaughtered broiler, according to the drawn samples.

Table (1): Isolation of *campylobacter* spp. from broiler intestine, de-feathering machines and carcass rinse water.

Region	broiler intestine		De-feathering machines		carcass rinse water		Total		
	Examined sample	Positive sample	Examined sample	Positive sample	Examined sample	Positive sample	Examined sample	Positive sample	
Hay Al-Nser	10	6(60%)	10	0 (0%)	10	1 (10%)	30	7(23.33%)	
Hay Al-Hur	10	6(60%)	10	1 (10%)	10	1 (10%)	30	8(26.67%)	
Hay Al-Ghader	10	7(70%)	10	2 (20%)	10	2 (20%)	30	11(36.67%)	
Feriha	10	7(70%)	10	1 (10%)	10	1 (10%)	30	9(30%)	
Groun d Total	40	26(65%)	40	4 (10%)	40	5(12.5%)	120	35(29.16%)	
Chi-square	x²=37.3512605					p-value ≤0.01		x²=1.41	p-value >0.05

Our findings in table (2) show that there is no significant (p-value ≥0.05) difference between local and imported frozen chicken.

Table (2): Isolation of *campylobacter* spp. from frozen carcass

Frozen carcass	Examined sample	Positive sample	Chi-square
Local	20	3 (15%)	x²= 3.24 p-value>0.05
Imported	20	0 (0%)	
Total number	40	3 (7.5%)	

1.2. Prevalence of *Campylobacter* spp. in Human

Out of 100 stool samples 6 (6%) yielded *Campylobacter* species on culture for the 20 (from birth-5years) samples, the detection rate was **20%**, while, **5%** (5-10 years), also **5%** for (10-15 years) as shown in table (3). However, *Campylobacter* spp. could not have been isolated from samples collected from categories above 15 years of age

Our finding shown in table (3) proves that there is a significant (**p-value ≤ 0.05**) correlation between age and infection with *campylobacter* spp., as the results show high infections in children under five years of age, and the incidence rate decreases with increasing age.

Table (3): Isolation of *campylobacter* spp. from human stool sample

Age	Examined Sample	Positive Sample
From birth - up to 5 years	20	4 (20%)
5 years - 10 years	20	1 (5%)
10years - 15 years	20	1 (5%)
15 years - 30 years	20	0 (0%)
Above 30 years	20	0 (0%)
<u>Total number</u>	100	6 (6%)
<u>Chi-square</u>	x²=9.574468085	p-value ≤ 0.05

Discussion

1. Prevalence in Broilers Chicken.

The incidence of campylobacteriosis has been on the rise during the last ten years. Due to *Campylobacter* spp. capacity to colonize poultry intestine and poultry meat serves as a reservoir for campylobacteriosis in food (Ayaz et al., 2016). The primary method of infection transmission is through the consumption of foods of an animal origin, particularly chicken meat (Butzler and Oosterom,1991).

The highest occurrence of *Campylobacter* (36.7%) in broiler meat was detected in 2016 reported by some European member state. In 2011 nationwide survey on raw chicken on retail sales in the Republic of Ireland (ROI) revealed *Campylobacter* was detected in 50.2% of samples using a quantitative method, with bacteria counts ranging from of 10 CFU/g, to of 61,000 CFU/g.

Our findings demonstrated that the prevalence of *Campylobacter* in poultry flocks was 23.75% These results agree with the findings of other studies, in which the prevalence rate of *Campylobacter* recovered from poultry was ranged between 22.4 %to 27.4% (Youseef et al., 2017; Rossler et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2020; Mahdi et al., 2022; Gharbi et al., 2018).

Conversely, current data showed that the *Campylobacter* prevalence was higher than that reported in Iraq and Egypt among samples collected from birds and humans (Al-Nasrawi, 2016; Abushahba et al., 2018). However, our results were lower than that recorded in several studies published elsewhere by Greige et al. (2019), Adiguze et al., (2018) and Meldrum et al., (2005).

From the current study, results showed in table (1), it turns out that there is a correlation between the bacteria and the site of infection, where the evidence showed a significant increase in the intestine when compared to De-feathering machines and carcass rinse water (p-value ≤ 0.01). Regarding poultry as representing the largest reservoir of *campylobacter* spp. The present finding demonstrated that the isolation rates of *campylobacter* spp. in broiler chicken intestine were indeed high ranged 16.25 per cent as shown in table (1).

The isolates obtained from de-feathering machine and washing water were few compared to the number of isolates obtained from chicken intestines and the reason for this is due to the fact that the intestine provides a suitable environment for *Campylobacter* growth from anaerobic conditions, nutrients and temperature. While when these bacteria are exposed to atmospheric air, their numbers decrease widely as a result of exposure to oxygen, temperature change and other conditions.

The main sites of colonization are the caeca, colon and cloaca of the bird, where varying levels up to log₉ per gram of contents can occur (Berndtson et al., 1992; Stern et al., 1999; Berrang et al., 2000). Thermophilic *campylobacters* are highly adapted to conditions in the avian GI tract and their optimum growth temperature of 42°C is close to the body temperature of the bird.

2. Prevalence in Human.

From the current study, out of 100 stool samples 6 (6%) yielded *Campylobacter* species on culture. Table (3) shows that there is a significant (p-value ≤ 0.05) correlation between age and infection with *campylobacter* spp., as the results show high infections in children under five years of age, and the incidence rate decreases with increasing age.

The results showed that the high infection rate among age group ranging from 2 month-5 years 4 cases, (20%) positive by culture assay and the least affected group was 5-15 years 2 out of 40 cases (5%) positive by culture assay respectively as shown in table (3) This result was consistent with study in Al-Diwanya, Iraq by ALHamadani and Saleh (2011) who found that *Campylobacter* is one of causes of diarrhea in children with age less than one-year-old.

This overall recovery rate of *Campylobacter* was compatible with the study in al Diwanyiah governorate by AL-Hamadani and Saleh 2011 who found that the percentage of *Campylobacter* was (9%) in children with positive *Campylobacter* culture. The prevalence of isolation *Campylobacter* species among diarrheic children was reported to be 5.4% in Turkey (Kayman et al., 2013). Seven percent in India (Mukherjee et al., 2013) and 11.1% in Lebanon (Dabboussi et al., 2012). As reported by WHO and FAO 2012, the incidence of *Campylobacteriosis* was 9.3 per 1,000 people in Europe America. *Campylobacter* is 1 of 4 key global causes of diarrhoeal diseases. It is considered to be the most common bacterial cause of human gastroenteritis in the world.

Shams et al., 2017 and Ghorbanalizadgan et al., 2014 recorded that percentage of isolation positive cases with *Campylobacter* was 4.5% which detected by culture method. Low recovery rate by culture method may be due to fastidious nature of bacterium, self-limitation of *C. jejuni* and may be conflicted several factors which are difficult to control, causes difficulty with the culturing of the organism, such as contamination, presence of intestinal flora, loss of viability of organism during transportation. All these may be responsible for a negative predictive value associated with culture of *Campylobacter*.

Kotloff et al., (2013) found that *Campylobacter* infection was not significantly associated with any age group isolated from different site in African. Also, in Brazil, Veras et al. (2007) found that presenting significant association between the presence of the *C. jejuni* in children aged 0-12 months. WHO 2012, demonstrated that *Campylobacter* infections in children under the age of 2 years are especially frequent, sometimes resulting in death. In developing countries where *Campylobacter* is endemic, infection is usually limited to children, with illness/infection ratios decreasing with age, suggesting that exposure in early life might lead to the development of protective immunity (Kaakoush et al., 2015).

The results of the current study and other similar studies proved that the most effective age with *Campylobacter* is under five years that is due to their immunity system is incomplete and the *Campylobacter* infection is consider as self-limited disease depended on immune system.

References

- AL-Hamadani, A. H. and Saleh Z.F. (2011). Detection of *Campylobacter* spp. in children diarrhea by using Polymerase Chain Reaction PCR technique in AlDiwanyiah Governorate. AL-Qadisiya Journal of Vet.Med.Sci. Vol./10. No./2. Pp: 45-54.
- Al-Juboori. A. F. A. (2012). Study of Pathological and Immunological Effects of *Campylobacter jejuni* Hepatotoxin on Laboratory Animals. phd. thesis, Babylon University, Iraq.
- Aryal, S. (2018). Oxidase Test-Principle, Uses, Procedure, Types, Result Interpretation, Examples and Limitations. Last updated.
- Ayaz ND, Goncuoglu M, Cakmak O, Erol I (2016): Comparison of *hipO* and *ceuE* Gene Based PCR Assays for the Detection of *Campylobacter Jejuni*. J Clin Microbiol Biochem Technol 2(1): 006-008.
- BEERY, J.T., HUGDAHL, M.B. and DOYLE, M.P. (1 988) Colonization of the gastrointestinal tract of chicks by *Campylobacter jejuni*. Applied and Environmental Microbiology 54: 2365-2370
- BEIRNDTSON, E., TIVEMO, M. and ENGVALL, A. (1992) Distribution and numbers of *Campylobacter* in
- BERRANG, M.E., BUHR, R.J. and CASON, J.A. (2000) *Campylobacter* recovery from external and internal organs of commercial broiler carcasses prior to scalding. Poultry Science 79: 286-290.
- Butzler, J.P. and Oosterom, J. (1991): *Campylobacter*: pathogenicity and significance in foods. International Journal of Food Microbiology 12, 1–8.

- Dabboussi F, Alam S, Mallat H, Hlais S, Hamze M. (2012). Preliminary study on the prevalence of *Campylobacter* in childhood diarrhoea in north Lebanon. *East Mediterr Health J*; 18(12): 1225-8.
- Fitzgerald, C. (2015). *Campylobacter*. *Clinics in Laboratory Medicine*, 35(2), 289-298.
- Fonseca, T.L.; Moraes, E.P.; Juliano, C.R.; Silva, A.M.; Scaini, C.J. MendozaSassi, R.A. and Silva, P.E.A. (2010). Detection of *Helicobacter pylori* by Phenotypic and Genotypic Methods. *Dig Dis Sci*. 55:1643–1648.
- Food Safety Authority Ireland (FSAI). Survey to Determine the Prevalence of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* on Raw Chicken on Retail Sale in Ireland in 2011 (11NS2). 2016, 21.
- Ghorbanalizadgan M., Bakhshi B., Lili A. K., Najjar-Peerayeh S. and Nikmanesh B., (2014). A Molecular Survey of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter Coli* Virulence and Diversity. *Iranian Biomedical Journal* 18 (3): 158-164.
- Grzybowska-Chlebowczyk U., Kalita B., Flak-Wancerz A., Jasielska M, Więcek S, Wojcieszyn M, Horowska-Ziaja S, Chlebowczyk W, Woś H .(2013). Clinical course of *Campylobacter* infections in children. *p e diatriapolska* 88: 3 2 9 – 3 3 4.
- Hasso, S. A. (2018). Epidemiological study of thermophilic *Campylobacter* isolated from diarrheic and non-diarrheic cows in Baghdad governorate. *Iraqi Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 42(1), 105-113.
- HIJGDAHL, M.B., BEERY, J.T. and DOYLE, M.P. (1988) Chemotactic behaviour of *Campylobacter jejuni*. *Infection and Immunity* 56: 1560-1566.
- Isabel, R. (2019). *Campylobacter jejuni* bacteremia in a patient with asplenia and enteritis. *IDCases*, 17, e00555.
- James A. Platts-Mills, Jie Liu, Jean Gratz, Esto Mduma, Caroline Amour, Ndealilia Swai, Mami Taniuchi, Sharmin Begum, Pablo Peñataro Yori, Drake H. Tilley, Gwenyth Lee, Zeli Shen, Mark T. Whary, James G. Fox, Monica McGrath, Margaret Kosek, Rashidul Haque, Eric R. Houpt. (2014). Detection of *Campylobacter* in Stool and Determination of Significance by Culture, Enzyme Immunoassay, and PCR in Developing Countries. *J Clin Microbiol*; 52(4): 1074–1080.
- Kaakoush NO, Castaño-Rodríguez N, Mitchell HM, Man SM. (2015). Global epidemiology of *Campylobacter* infection. *Clin Microbiol Rev* doi:10.1128/CMR.00006-15.
- Kalmokoff, M., Lanthier, P., Tremblay, T.-L., Foss, M., Lau, P. C., Sanders, G., Austin, J., Kelly, J. and Szymanski, C. M. (2006) Proteomic Analysis of *Campylobacter jejuni* 11168 Biofilms Reveals a Role for the Motility Complex in Biofilm Formation. *J Bacteriol*, 188(12), pp. 4312-4320.
- Kandasamy, S., Vlasova, A. N., Fischer, D. D., Chattha, K. S., Shao, L., Kumar, A., ... & Saif, L. J. (2017). Unraveling the differences between gram-positive and gram-negative probiotics in modulating protective immunity to enteric infections. *Frontiers in immunology*, 8, 334.
- Kayman T, Abay S, Hizlisoy H. (2013). Identification of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates with phenotypic methods and multiplex polymerase chain reaction and their antibiotic susceptibilities. *Mikrobiyol Bul*; 47(2):230-9.

- Mahdi, D. M., Alhatami, A. O., & Muhsen, H. (2022, January). Phenotypic and genotypic in identification of genus *Campylobacter* from broilers. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 2386, No. 1, p. 020009). AIP Publishing LLC.
- Merino, F. J., Agulla, A. N. D. R. E. S., Villasante, P. A., Díaz, A. U. R. O. R. A., Saz, J. V., & Velasco, A. C. (1986). Comparative efficacy of seven selective media for isolating *Campylobacter jejuni*. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 24(3), 451-452.
- Mukherjee P, Ramamurthy T, Bhattacharya MK, Rajendran K, Mukhopadhyay AK. (2013). *Campylobacter jejuni* in hospitalized patients with diarrhea, Kolkata, India. *Emerg Infectious Dis*; 19(7): 1155-6.
- Mukhopadhyaya, I., Thomson, J. M., Hansen, R., Berry, S. H., El-Omar, E. M., & Hold, G. L. (2011). Detection of *Campylobacter concisus* and other *Campylobacter* species in colonic biopsies from adults with ulcerative colitis. *PloS one*, 6(6), e21490.
- Mushi, M. F., Paterno, L., Tappe, D., Pendo, A., Seni, J., Moremi, N., ... & Mshana, S. E. (2014). Evaluation of detection methods for *Campylobacter* infections among under-fives in Mwanza City, Tanzania. *Pan African Medical Journal*, 19(1).
newly slaughtered broiler chickens and hens. *International Journal of Food Microbiology* 15: 45-50.
- PÉREZ-PÉREZ, G. I., & Blaser, M. J. (1996). *Campylobacter* and *Helicobacter*-medical microbiology. University of Texas Medical Branch, Galveston, 1.
- Popovic-Uroic, T. A. T. J. A. N. A., Patton, C. M., Nicholson, M. A., & Kiehlbauch, J. A. (1990). Evaluation of the indoxyl acetate hydrolysis test for rapid differentiation of *Campylobacter*, *Helicobacter*, and *Wolinella* species. *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 28(10), 2335-2339.
- Shakir, Z. M., Alhatami, A. O., Ismail Khudhair, Y., & Muhsen Abdulwahab, H. (2021). Antibiotic Resistance Profile and Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index of *Campylobacter* Species Isolated from Poultry. *Archives of Razi Institute*, 76(6), 1677-1686.
- Shams S., Ghorbanalizadgan M., Mahmmodi h., Piccirillo A., (2017). Evaluation of a Multiplex PCR Assay for the Identification of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli*. *Infect Epidemiol Med*. Winter; Volume 3, Issue 1: 6-8.
- STERN, N.J., BAILEY, J.S., COX, N.A., CRAVEN, S.E. and CRAY, P.F. (1999) Flow of *Campylobacter* spp. through US poultry operations. In: 10th International Workshop on *Campylobacter*; *Helicobacter* and Related Organisms (Mobley, H.L.T, Nachamkin, I. and McGee, D., Eds) Abstract no. CF17, Baltimore, USA.
- Vandamme, P., Dewhirst, F. E., Paster, B. J., & On, S. L. (2015). *Campylobacter*. *Bergey's Manual of Systematics of Archaea and Bacteria*, 1-27.
- Veras, H.N., Rodrigues, T. S., Quetz, J. S., Freitas, T.M., Filho, J.Q., Lima, I.F.N., Havt, A., Mota, R.M.S., Rey, L.C.; Guerrant, R.L., Lima, A.A.M. (2007). Molecular diagnosis and virulence genes profile from *Campylobacter jejuni* infection isolated from children with moderate to severe diarrhea in Fortaleza, Ceara, Brazil. ##

Weingarten, R. A., Grimes, J. L., & Olson, J. W. (2008). Role of *Campylobacter jejuni* respiratory oxidases and reductases in host colonization. *Applied and environmental microbiology*, 74(5), 1367-1375.

WHO and FAO. (2017) The global view of campylobacteriosis: report of an expert consultation. [foodsafety/publications/foodborne_disease/global_view_campylobacteriosis/en/.htm](https://www.who.int/publications/foodborne_disease/global_view_campylobacteriosis/en/) www.who.int/.